

Quantifying the impact of a circular economy in buildings on industry decarbonisation: Integrating material flow and industry modelling

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ABSTRACT

A circular economy can contribute to reduce the demand for emission-intensive basic materials and to efficiently decarbonize the industry. However, current energy system models are not able to adequately depict this contribution in industry transformation pathways to guide policy making. To address this gap, we integrated material flow and industry modelling for a circular economy in buildings. Results show that a circular economy in buildings addressing material production, building design, and building use could reduce industrial material production, captured emissions, energy demand and cumulated costs for industry decarbonisation. It reduces particularly the use of hydrogen and carbon capture, which are associated with implementation barriers. The findings imply that a circular economy could contribute to the decarbonisation of the industry sector and that it is necessary to develop new policies that split financial burdens, incentivize collaborations and facilitate the more intense use of buildings.

1. Introduction

The industry sector of the European Union (EU) was responsible for 20 % of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in 2022 (European Environment Agency, 2023a). Reducing these GHG emissions by 2050 is crucial to achieve the climate targets set out in the European long-term strategy (European Commission, 2018). This is especially important for the production of basic material given high production volumes and emissions, e.g. the production of steel and cement was responsible for around two-thirds of the 2022 EU industry sector emissions (European Environment Agency, 2023b). Construction is one of the largest users of these materials, i.e. over one third of steel and the complete cement consumption (Cembureau, 2023; Eurofer, 2023). In detail, around 29 % of steel and 36 % of cement consumption is used for buildings (Cembureau, 2023; Rostek et al., 2022). For construction, mostly long steel products are used, which are typically made from secondary steel related to lower GHG emissions than primary production (Cullen, 2017; Pauliuk et al., 2017). The production of cement is related to a significant share of process-related emissions from clinker production (Shanks et al., 2019). Production of construction materials for buildings accounted for 6 % of EU GHG emissions in 2020 (BPiE et al., 2023).

While it is possible to decarbonise the production of steel and cement, it is associated with high costs, which could increase production costs by up to 15 % and 30 % (Andersson, 2023; Gailani et al., 2024). Reducing the demand for these primary materials in building construction can contribute to efficiently decarbonise the industry (Karlsson et al., 2020). The circular economy (CE) gains momentum to achieve this reduction (Pauliuk et al., 2021; Zhong et al., 2021). However, current energy system models that are used to support policy making do not consider the full potential of a CE in the analysis of decarbonisation strategies. In particular, models used to analyse EU industry decarbonisation scenarios, so-called industry sector simulation models or short industry models, are not able to completely and robustly depict the contribution of the full scope of a CE (I2AM Paris, 2024). Linking such models with material flow analysis (MFA) could improve this by explicitly modelling material flows and stocks (Corona et al., 2019; Kullmann et al., 2021).

The novelty of this paper is twofold: First, modelling the impact of a broad range of CE potentials in buildings on steel and cement production and second, linking these results to an industry model to assess their impact on GHG emissions, energy demand and costs in the industry sector. Thus, this paper addresses the research questions: *What is the*

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impact of a comprehensive CE in residential and commercial buildings on the decarbonisation of the EU industry sector?

2. Literature review

2.1. Decarbonising steel and cement production

The emission-intensive primary production of steel in the blast furnace and basic oxygen furnace (BF/BOF) can be substituted by hydrogen direct reduction (H₂-DRI) or the emissions can be captured (Gailani et al., 2024). Hydrogen production is associated with a variety of challenges, e.g. limited availability of (green) hydrogen in the short to medium term, high demand for (renewable) electricity, expected increase of worldwide production costs by 15 % (depending on hydrogen prices) and potential import dependencies (Gailani et al., 2024; Wetzel et al., 2023). Carbon capture is associated with techno-economic limitations and social barriers related to the carbon sink, e.g. the utilization in other production processes (CCU) or storage (CCS). Also, it requires the development of new infrastructure to transport CO₂ (Gailani et al., 2024). Increased recycling of steel in the electric arc furnace (EAF) can be a very efficient way to replace blast furnaces, but is limited by quality requirements and scrap availability (Dworak et al., 2022).

In contrast to steel, no industrial-scale alternative technologies are available to avoid process-related emissions during the production of cement and its precursor clinker. GHG emissions can be reduced but not completely avoided by reducing the share of clinker in cement or of cement in concrete. Moreover, material substitutes can be used, such as alternative binders, industry by-products or calcined clays (Ishak and Hashim, 2015; Shanks et al., 2019). Thus, the final option is carbon capture, which is associated with the above-mentioned challenges. Cement production costs are expected to increase globally by up to 30 % (Gailani et al., 2024).

2.2. Circular economy in buildings

The CE concept is not new but offers a new framing for various strategies (Blomsma and Brennan, 2017). Earlier descriptions focus strongly on the recycling of material while newer approaches, such as the 10R framework, include a broad range from the smarter use of products over the extended lifespan to the efficient application of materials (Boulding, 1966; Çimen, 2021; Kirchherr et al., 2017).

For the case of buildings, few studies modelled the impact of a CE on decarbonisation. Karlsson et al. (2020) focus on decarbonising the Swedish basic material production. This study does not consider the full scope of the 10R framework but does include well-established R-strategies for the production stage, such as recycle or reduce. These technical and well-known strategies could reduce the GHG emissions for steel production by up to 50 % and for cement by up to 70 % compared to current levels. The global studies by Pauliuk et al. (2021) and Zhong et al. (2021) focus on the use stage of buildings, including less established R-strategies, such as refuse or replace. These strategies require a deepened CE implementation through behavioural change and the collaboration of stakeholders along the value chain. Various non-academic studies confirm the role of a comprehensive CE in buildings for decarbonisation. For example, the International Resource Panel (2020) reports decarbonisation potentials of around -35 % GHG emissions for the G7 countries in 2050 compared to 2016 related to the full scope of the 10R framework. Similar potentials for the global level were published by Material Economics (2018) and Circle Economy (2024). The studies show the relevance of a CE in buildings for decarbonisation, but also how different system boundaries in the analysis affect the results, i.e. varying region, time frame and CE actions.

Most available studies focus on CE potentials in isolation and miss the interplay with other decarbonisation strategies, such as fuel switching or CCU/S. Such strategies, however, strongly affect the impact of CE on decarbonisation and vice versa. Only Karlsson et al. (2020)

consider the CE in combination with other strategies for industry decarbonisation. Anyhow, the study is limited by its scope, i.e. the analysis on the national level and focus on selected R-strategies.

2.3. Modelling circular economy and decarbonisation

The I2AM Paris (2024) platform reports 21 established and extensively used models to analyse prospective decarbonisation scenarios and guide policy making in Europe. Of these 21 models, five include decarbonisation of industry. Two of them, the EU-Times and the LEAP model, do not consider a CE as they rely on production projections as input data (Nijs and Ruiz Castello, 2019; Stockholm Environment Institute, 2024). The three other models can depict certain CE strategies. The EnergyPLAN and the WISEE-EDM model consider recycling (Aalborg University, 2024; Schneider and Saurat, 2020). In addition to recycling, the FORECAST model integrates material efficiency via exogenous material-specific assumptions (Fleiter et al., 2019, 2018). So, while there are approaches to account for CE strategies in industry decarbonisation scenarios, these are limited to a lower CE implementation depth neglecting changes during the use phase. Moreover, the applied methods also restrict the modelling of the considered strategies, i.e. recycling and material efficiency. The availability of secondary material is often not incorporated as limiting factor for recycling, while material efficiency is considered top-down and not bottom-up for individual products, limiting the robustness of the material-specific assumptions. Thus, the industry models fail to capture the full potential of a CE in combination with other industry decarbonisation strategies and the quality of how they consider CE strongly depends on exogenous assumptions.

The linkage of such models with MFA could overcome these shortcomings as well as the limitations related to the modelling of CE potentials for buildings mentioned in the previous section (Corona et al., 2019; Kullmann et al., 2021). As shown by Herbst et al. (2023), combining an industry model with an MFA can increase the robustness of model inputs by overcoming the shortcomings and limitations while better quantifying energy system impacts and costs.

MFA assess material flows between value chain stages and the accumulation of material stocks (Pauliuk et al., 2015). The following MFA characteristics are relevant for modelling CE and industry decarbonisation:

- *Stock-driven MFA* determines material inflows from lifetime distributions and the material stocks required to fulfil a service demand (Pauliuk and Hertwich, 2016). The extrapolation of stocks is less sensitive to fluctuations than extrapolating material inflows, particularly for products with a long lifetime, such as buildings (Lauinger et al., 2021). Especially when developing scenarios to guide policy making, it is crucial to off-set short-term fluctuations and focus on long-term drivers to design transformational policies (Störmer et al., 2020).
- *Dynamic MFA* models the accumulation of material stocks between years. This is necessary for assessing material outflows from the stock, i.e. the secondary material availability (Deng et al., 2023). By doing so, it is possible to consider secondary material availability as limiting factor for recycling-based processes in industry models. This improves the robustness of model inputs relating to the potential contribution of secondary production (Herbst et al., 2023).
- *Bottom-up MFA* aggregates product-specific material flows (Pauliuk et al., 2015). Such analyses are characterized by a high level of detail and extensive data requirements (Villalba et al., 2018). This enables the assessment of product-specific CE actions and in particular changes in product use and design. Consequently, this improves the accuracy of model inputs for industry models. However, the high level of detail may also be a limitation, as not all materials covered by the industry models can be considered with the same depth.

3. Material and methods

3.1. Scenario definition

We defined a reference and a decarbonisation scenario and used three variants for each of these. The reference and decarbonisation scenario were based on [Yu et al. \(2023\)](#) and depicted two fundamentally different directions for the EU industry sector. The reference scenario considers currently implemented EU policies but no further policies or measures for achieving climate targets. The decarbonisation scenario, in contrast, achieves the EU climate targets by 2050 through strong decarbonisation policies and measures. These two scenarios allowed to compare the impact of a CE for a reference not achieving climate targets and for a decarbonised industry sector. This enabled to quantify the full potential of a CE for industry decarbonisation. The three additional variants of each of these scenarios consider the effects of a CE in buildings compared to the baseline scenario.

To consider the effects of a CE in buildings, we formulated three so-called CE bundles reflected by the three scenario variants. As suggested by [Lotz, Rosales Carreón et al. \(2024\)](#), the bundles comprise an increasing number of CE actions to reflect an increasing CE implementation depth along the building value chain. Bundle I reflects a low CE implementation depth and includes upstream CE actions addressing the production of building materials, i.e. increased material efficiency during production and the exploitation of secondary production routes. Bundle II comprises a moderate implementation depth, i.e. midstream CE actions in addition to the upstream CE actions covered by bundle I, like timber construction, material efficient design of buildings, and the reuse of buildings components and materials. Finally, bundle III covers additional downstream CE actions, such as the more efficient use of floor space and the lifetime extension of buildings. An ambitious but realistic implementation is assumed for the individual actions to analyse the potential of a CE.

3.2. Models

3.2.1. Stock-driven material flow modelling approach

We applied the approach of [Lotz, Herbst, et al. \(2024\)](#) and varied key model parameters to reflect the effect of a CE in buildings on material production. The general approach corresponds to a bottom-up, dynamic, stock-driven MFA. The MFA covers steel, concrete, cement and clinker stocks and flows related to residential and commercial buildings in the 27 EU member states from 2020 to 2050. Key model parameters that were varied to reflect a CE are the buildings stock development, material intensities, process parameters or reuse- and recycling shares. The order of calculating the impact is determined by the hierarchy in the 10R framework.

The resulting changes in steel, cement and clinker production were transferred to the industry sector model described below.

3.2.2. Industry sector simulation model FORECAST

FORECAST is a bottom-up industry model, which calculates long-term pathways for GHG emissions and energy demand in the industry and its sub-sectors ([Fleiter et al., 2018](#)). The model is designed to cover the entire industry sector and uses a bottom-up approach for major energy-intensive industries by specifically considering individual production processes. Input data comprise main drivers of energy demand and technical change like physical and economic activity and energy prices, policy parameters, structural information, and additional technology diffusion parameters. With the physical activity being a main driver of the model, it is well suited to link with MFA approaches. Technology diffusion is modelled for specifically defined technologies. This technology detail allows a high accuracy when calculating resulting impacts on energy demand or costs. The model considers major decarbonisation strategies, such as switch to carbon-neutral processes and energy carriers as well as carbon capture and energy efficiency.

To feed the results of the material flow into the FORECAST model, we subtracted the changes in steel, cement, and clinker production for buildings from the total industrial material production. First, the change in building material production was distributed according to the process shares in each EU member state in the baseline projection of total material production. Then, the change in building material production was offset with this baseline projection of total material production. This approach is based on two main assumptions: (1) The reduction in material production only reduces domestic production, not imports and (2) the reduction in material production only affects primary production processes, secondary production potentials remain unchanged.

We calculated the following indicators: GHG emissions, final energy demand and technical costs, i.e. energy expenditures,¹ CO₂ costs² and investments.³

3.3. Data and assumptions

3.3.1. Input data for the material flow modelling

The baseline projection against which the impact of the CE bundles was assessed is presented in [Lotz, Herbst, et al. \(2024\)](#). It is based on the EU Reference Scenario published by the [European Commission \(2021\)](#) for the building stock development as well as 75 residential and commercial building material intensities. This baseline projection assumes that material demand for EU buildings will increase across EU member states due to a growing building stock. For this paper, the baseline was linearly interpolated to compensate for strong fluctuations in new construction resulting from discontinuous replacement of old buildings driven by building age and lifetime. Detailed information on the model inputs for the baseline projection are described in the Supporting Information A.1.1.

Based on [Lotz, Rosales Carreón, et al. \(2024\)](#), we formulated and parameterized three CE bundles, which are assessed against the baseline projection of building material demand. Detailed information on the bundles and their parameterisation can be found in the Supporting Information A.1.2.

3.3.2. Input data for the industry modelling

Besides the total material production, the industry model uses the specific energy consumption (SEC) and technology costs of production processes as well as energy and CO₂ prices.

The baseline projection for the total material production (not considering CE actions) was based on the assumptions and input data presented in the Supporting Information A.2.1. In detail, it was driven by historic production trends, projections of macroeconomic framework data in line with the European Reference scenario published by the [European Commission \(2021\)](#) and own assumptions on the development of gross value added (GVA) as well as the diffusion of carbon-neutral production processes. It should be noted that these are assumptions and inherently uncertain. They are, however, useful to describe – in comparison – the effects of CE actions. For this purpose, we offset the change in building material production as a result of the three modelled CE bundles with the baseline projection of total material production to generate three variants of the total material production.

The relevant input data and assumptions on production processes and prices are presented in the Supporting Information A.2.2.

¹ Energy expenditures are determined annually from the energy carrier price and energy carrier demand.

² CO₂ costs are defined as the annual sum of costs for energy- and process-related emissions multiplied with a CO₂ price differentiating sectors covered by the emission trading scheme (ETS) and not covered by the ETS.

³ Investments include upfront investments as well as operational expenditures excluding energy expenditures for efficiency improvements, fuel switch and innovative processes including the CO₂ infrastructure system.

4. Results

4.1. Results of the material flow analysis

Fig. 1 presents the changes in material flows for EU buildings in 2050 related to the three CE bundles resulting from the material flow model. In general, the sum of the sub-flows reflects the baseline projection for each flow. The only exception is the building element reuse, which is not part of the baseline. Thus, the sum of the sub-flows for the building element reuse corresponds to bundle II. The individual sub-flows show the reduction related to each CE bundle as well as the remaining flows related to bundle III. Accordingly, increasing CE implementation depth leads to an increased reduction in material demand and production. Consequently, bundle III leads to the highest reduction in basic material production: 11 Mt steel, 25 Mt cement and 23 Mt clinker. In comparison to bundle II the additional absolute reduction related to bundle III is moderate. Bundle II leads to an absolute reduction by 2050 of 8 Mt steel and 16 Mt cement production. Still, bundle III significantly reduces waste generation, i.e. the outflow from the use phase. For clinker production, the largest reduction of 11 Mt is caused by bundle I, i.e. a comparably low CE implementation depth. Thus, bundle I is relevant for industry decarbonisation due to the high emission intensity of clinker production, even though it does not affect steel production.

Table 1 breaks down the relationships between CE actions by presenting the relative non-additive contribution of the CE actions in each bundle to the reduction of basic material production for buildings. As the individual CE actions are addressing different points in the same value chain, they affect each other in their possible impact on material production. For instance, the more efficient design of buildings decreases the demand for concrete and its precursors and a decreasing demand for new buildings and reduces the use of new materials, such as timber. The table shows that the reduction of cement and clinker production related to CE actions from bundle I decreases in bundle II from 10 % to 7 % and 35 % to 24 %, respectively. A similar relationship along the value chain can be observed for bundle II and bundle III. While the reduction related to individual CE actions is decreased by the combination with further

Table 1

Relative reduction compared to the baseline projection of the circular economy actions in the bundles I, II and III in annual steel, cement, and clinker production for buildings in the European Union in 2050.

		Steel production	Cement production	Clinker production
Bundle I	Total	0 %	-10 %	-35 %
	Actions in bundle I	0 %	-10 %	-35 %
Bundle II	Total	-46 %	-52 %	-66 %
	Actions in bundle I	0 %	-7 %	-24 %
	Additional actions in bundle II	-46 %	-45 %	-42 %
Bundle III	Total	-61 %	-65 %	-75 %
	Actions in bundle I	0 %	-6 %	-18 %
	Additional actions in bundle II	-35 %	-34 %	-35 %
	Additional actions in bundle III	-27 %	-25 %	-22 %

actions, the bundled implementation still has a higher total impact on basic material production than the individual CE actions.

Finally, Fig. 2 presents the results of the material flow model for steel, cement, and clinker production according to the steel and concrete inflow for EU buildings in 2020 to 2050. These results are fed into the industry model. The baseline projection against which the CE impact is assessed assumes that without additional action, the production of basic materials for EU buildings increases between 2020 and 2050 by nearly 60 %. A CE can reduce this projected basic material production. In line with the increasing CE implementation depth, bundle III is associated with the highest reduction. With these impacts, CE actions in bundle III overcompensate the increasing trend for all products and result in a substantial reduction of demand and production in the long term. Note

Fig. 1. Changes in material flows for EU buildings related to the circular economy bundles I, II and III in 2050.

Fig. 2. Absolute reduction compared to the baseline projection of the circular economy bundles I, II and II in steel, cement and clinker production for buildings in the European Union between 2020 and 2050.

Fig. 3. Greenhouse gas emissions of the sub-sectors iron and steel and non-metallic minerals calibrated to the national inventories differentiated by source for the reference and decarbonisation scenario in the European Union in 2020, 2030 and 2050.

that even a moderate depth of implementation (bundle II) has a noteworthy influence on basic material production.

4.2. Results of the industry model

The results of the industry model FORECAST include the GHG emissions (Fig. 3), the final energy demand (FED, Table 2) and costs (Table 3) of the sub-sectors relevant for our analysis, namely iron and steel and non-metallic minerals. While we differentiate a reference and a decarbonisation scenario for the GHG emissions, we focus solely on the decarbonisation scenario for the FED and costs.

In the reference scenario, the CE bundles lead to a reduction of GHG emissions for the selected sub-sectors in the year 2050: 2 % for bundle I (5 Mt CO₂eq), 8 % for bundle II (19 Mt CO₂eq) and 10 % for bundle III (23 Mt CO₂eq). Consequently, the differences of bundle I, II and III revealed for the total material production are also visible for the GHG emissions. The decarbonisation scenario includes a high level of emission reduction already in the baseline case. It is driven by the deployment of new technologies, electrification, hydrogen, and CCS, which are associated with high costs. Due to the scenario philosophy, the absolute reduction of GHG emissions is – in all bundles – minor compared to the decarbonisation baseline in the year 2050 (around 2 Mt CO₂eq for bundle III). However, the reference scenario variants clearly show the potential contribution of a CE in buildings to reduce GHG emission. The main impact of the CE bundles on GHG emissions in the decarbonisation scenario is a reduction in the amount of captured emissions by 5 % in bundle I (5 Mt CO₂eq), 9 % in bundle II (10 Mt CO₂eq) and 10 % in bundle III (12 Mt CO₂eq). This reduces the deployment of CCU/S required for achieving the climate targets and thus, the associated expenses.

Besides the change in captured emissions, further impacts of a CE in buildings on industry decarbonisation are related to the FED and energy carrier mix in the sub-sectors iron and steel and non-metallic minerals (Table 2). In the decarbonisation scenario, both sectors rely heavily on

Table 2

Absolute final energy demand and change compared to baseline for the sub-sectors iron and steel and non-metallic minerals differentiated by energy carrier for the decarbonisation scenario in the European Union in 2050.

		Iron and steel		Non-metallic minerals	
		TWh	Δ%	TWh	Δ%
Electricity	Baseline	156		131	
	Bundle I	156	0 %	130	-1 %
	Bundle II	148	-5 %	127	-3 %
	Bundle III	145	-7 %	125	-4 %
Hydrogen	Baseline	221		107	
	Bundle I	221	0 %	107	0 %
	Bundle II	199	-10 %	104	-2 %
	Bundle III	191	-13 %	103	-3 %
Fossil fuels	Baseline	12		2	
	Bundle I	12	0 %	2	0 %
	Bundle II	12	-7 %	2	-2 %
	Bundle III	11	-9 %	2	-3 %
RES	Baseline	9		31	
	Bundle I	9	0 %	31	1 %
	Bundle II	9	-5 %	30	-3 %
	Bundle III	9	-8 %	30	-5 %
Waste non-RES	Baseline	0		49	
	Bundle I	0	0 %	46	-7 %
	Bundle II	0	-6 %	43	-13 %
	Bundle III	0	-11 %	42	-15 %
Other	Baseline	8		16	
	Bundle I	8	0 %	16	0 %
	Bundle II	8	-4 %	16	-1 %
	Bundle III	8	-7 %	16	-1 %
Total	Baseline	398		305	
	Bundle I	398	0 %	300	-1 %
	Bundle II	366	-8 %	292	-4 %
	Bundle III	356	-11 %	288	-5 %

new technologies and fuel switching, which entail high costs. In the iron and steel sub-sector, the reduction of GHG emissions is achieved by switching to H₂-DRI for primary production, which is strongly affected by the impact of CE on steel demand for buildings. The total FED decrease – compared to the baseline in 2050 – by 8 % (32 TWh) and 11 % (43 TWh), while hydrogen is reduced by 10 % (22 TWh) and 13 % (29 TWh) in bundle II and III, respectively. For non-metallic minerals, decarbonisation in the baseline case is achieved by CCU/S and fuel switching to hydrogen, electricity, and non-renewable waste (waste non-RES). The use of waste is addressed over proportionally by a CE in buildings: The total FED is reduced – compared to the baseline in 2050 – by 1 % (4 TWh), 4 % (14 TWh) and 5 % (18 TWh) for bundle I, II and III respectively, while non-RES waste decreases by 7 % (3 TWh), 13 % (6 TWh) and 15 % (7 TWh). The use of non-RES waste is associated with the release of embedded emissions. Differences for the individual energy carriers result from the inclusion of other products, e.g. ceramics or glass, in this sub-sector, which are not addressed by the CE bundles. In comparison to the sub-sectoral average, a CE in buildings yields a disproportionately higher reduction of the use of potentially costly technologies and energy carriers, i.e. CCU/S and hydrogen.

Based on the results for GHG emissions and FED regarding hydrogen and CCU/S, the cost analysis focuses on energy expenditures, CO₂ costs and investments in carbon-neutral processes for the sub-sectors iron and steel and non-metallic minerals. The results presented in Table 3 differentiate the absolute and relative savings compared to the baseline decarbonisation scenario cumulated from 2020 to 2050 as well as the specific cost savings per tonne saved material. The highest total cumulated reduction is achieved by bundle III (72 bn€, of which 26 bn€ in iron and steel and 46 bn€ in non-metallic minerals). Bundle II reduces total cumulated costs by 47 bn€ (of which 14 bn€ in iron and steel and 33 bn€ in non-metallic minerals). In the sub-sector iron and steel, the investigated CE bundles reduce particularly the cumulated CO₂ costs and investments by up to 11 bn€ each. The CO₂ costs are particularly relevant during the beginning of the model period while the blast furnace has not yet been replaced with the H₂-DRI. In contrast, the investments become increasingly relevant closer to 2050 due to the investment needs in new production process, i.e. H₂-DRI. For non-metallic minerals, the CE bundles for buildings reduces mainly the operational costs or more precisely, CO₂ costs, by up to 42 bn€. In contrast to iron and steel, the reduction of cumulated investments is comparatively low as the investments in CCS are less costly than for H₂-DRI. Moreover, a slight increase (+1 to 2 bn€) of investments is noticeable related to the investigated CE bundles as the production of new cement types is associated to costs in the industry. Overall, the total costs are still decreasing (-18 to 46 bn€). The costs of the other CE actions are not included in the industry model. The specific cost savings indicate a threshold for additional costs for the other CE actions up to which a CE in buildings saves costs in context of industry decarbonisation.

5. Discussion

Our results confirm the relevance of a CE in buildings to reduce GHG emissions and facilitate industry decarbonisation – particularly due to reduction of FED, captured carbon and costs. In our analysis, we considered an increasing CE implementation depth, which also reflects the complexity of implementing the CE actions through the integration of several value chain stages (Lotz, Rosales Carreón, et al., 2024). One could argue that the increasing number of involved value chain stages and related actors imply increasing implementation efforts and growing unpredictability. For instance, CE actions related to the Refuse-strategy require on one hand behavioural change (e.g. the willingness to reduce living space) and on the other adaptations of the business models related to building design (e.g. developing building layouts allowing flexible use of living spaces) (Bierwirth and Thomas, 2019). It follows from this, that an increasing CE implementation depth may require additional policies to exploit their potentials as the current policy mix is insufficient

Table 3

Absolute, relative, and specific cost changes compared to the baseline decarbonisation scenario for the sub-sectors iron and steel and non-metallic minerals in the European Union cumulated between 2020 and 2050.

		Iron and steel			Non-metallic minerals		
		bn € 2017*	%	€/t steel**	bn € 2017*	%	€/t clinker**
Energy expenditure	Bundle I	0	0	0	-1	0	-7
	Bundle II	-2	-1	-36	-3	-1	-12
	Bundle III	-4	-2	-37	-5	-2	-18
CO ₂ costs	Bundle I	0	0	0	-18	-3	-122
	Bundle II	-4	-2	-79	-32	-4	-148
	Bundle III	-11	-5	-94	-42	-6	-143
Investment	Bundle I	0	0	0	2	2	11
	Bundle II	-7	-5	-138	1	2	6
	Bundle III	-11	-7	-98	1	1	2
Total	Bundle I	0	0	0	-18	-1	-118
	Bundle II	-14	-7	-253	-33	-4	-154
	Bundle III	-26	-14	-230	-46	-7	-159

*bn € 2017 corresponds to 10⁹ € nominal with the reference year 2017

**Cost savings per reduced tonne of steel or clinker as representative product from each sub-sector

(Leipold et al., 2022; Lotz et al., 2022). For instance, the downstream CE actions, such as reducing the clinker-to-cement ratio or concrete recycling, are well-addressed by the EU-ETS and the Waste Framework Directive (EU-ETS, 2003; Waste Framework Directive, 2008). In contrast, the policy coverage is lower and less uniform for midstream CE actions addressing building design. Current design practices are determined by the Eurocodes and other building regulations, e.g. fire safety (European Commission, n. d.). Updating these is crucial to allow alternative building design practices. Moreover, a cost increase can be expected during building design in relation to design for reuse and urban mining due to the increasing material demand and effort for deconstruction (Akbarnezhad et al., 2014). Thus, it is necessary to re-distribute downstream cost savings, for example through subsidies or public procurement (Ntsondé and Aggeri, 2021). Most challenging, however, is the exploitation of downstream potentials, i.e. new forms of service provision during the building use phase. While these CE actions can further decrease the basic material production at presumable lower costs, they are highly uncertain due to the required behavioural changes. Currently, no policy proposals are available to foster such a change. Nonetheless, these are the CE actions that potentially could have the most impact.

Our study has three main limitations. The first limitation arises from the inherent uncertainty of future developments. For the material flow modelling, this uncertainty not only concerns the CE actions but also the baseline projection. Particularly since there is no historical data on building material demand available with the same scope as our analysis to directly validate our results. The baseline projection could change disruptively due to economic and behavioural trends, which could imply a stagnating or even decreasing building stock growth. Less building stock growth would lead to decreasing material demand and thus, a lower absolute impact of the related CE actions. However, the availability of materials for reuse and recycling is not affected assuming that building lifetimes remain constant. Consequently, the relative impact of such CE actions increase compared to the present study. One conceivable approach to counter this uncertainty is to define further baseline projections and compare the absolute and relative impact of the CE bundles. The second limitation is related to the dynamic modelling of material stocks. The focus on one end use sector allows to consider the availability of materials for reuse and recycling from this sector alone. Steel scrap, however, is also generated and utilised in other end use sectors (Pauliuk et al., 2017). Inflow-driven MFA determining material stocks from material inflows, typically driven by extrapolated economic developments, allow to analyse future steel flows in all end use sectors (Villalba et al., 2018). It is thinkable to combine stock- and inflow-driven MFA to utilize their respective advantages when analysing CE actions. Finally, the last limitation arises from the bottom-up

material flow and industry modelling, which require a high level of data granularity. Consequently, the assumptions described in Section 3.2.2 were necessary to feed the material flow modelling outputs to the industry model. Such assumptions can potentially lead to inconsistencies, e.g. regarding secondary production potentials. Further validation and new assumptions regarding possible shifts between processes could increase the significance of the results. To enable this, the related data and assumptions are summarised in the Supporting Information.

Beyond the scope of the present analysis, further studies could benefit from implementing one (or all) of the following three suggestions. While the data availability on midstream and downstream cost related to CE actions is limited, considering these would enable the comparison with upstream cost savings. By doing so, it would be possible to weigh different decarbonisation options, e.g. new production processes vs. demand reduction. Moreover, our analysis is limited to one end use sector and does not consider the full potential of a CE across all end use sectors as well as interactions between these. Herbst et al. (2023) indicate that a complete transformation from a linear to a circular economy could further reduce the production of basic materials, related energy demand, and GHG emissions. Nevertheless, decarbonisation efforts are also necessary when considering a CE in further end use sectors. The integration of material flow and industry modelling can be extended to other end use sectors relevant for achieving the EU climate targets, for example transport (Wolfram et al., 2020). A combination of inflow- and stock driven material flow modelling approaches is conceivable to enable a complete depiction of end use products and trade flows. Such an extension should also consider other relevant basic materials, particularly plastics (Kajaste and Oinas, 2021). Finally, it is relevant to analyse further impacts of a CE, such as socioeconomic (e.g. macroeconomic implications), environmental (e.g. use of non-sustainable substitutes) or technical impacts (e.g. decreased energy infrastructure needs). Mapping the multiple facets of CE impacts is relevant against the backdrop of CE's diverse aims set out in literature, i. e. sustainability, economic development and social equity (Kirchherr et al., 2023; Leipold et al., 2022). While this is only possible to a limited extent with the applied methods, the combination with other approaches is promising (Nikas et al., 2022). For example, macro-economic methods could be integrated to assess impacts on employment or household spending, while wellbeing needs to be assessed as well. Life cycle analysis could analyse impacts on biodiversity, and energy system models could address supply-side implications. Such a holistic view enables the analysis of ambitious EU industry transformation pathways in line with climate and sustainable development targets.

6. Conclusion

This paper studied the impact of a broad range of CE actions in residential and commercial buildings on the decarbonisation of the EU industry by integrating material flow and industry modelling. The results showed that in 2050 such CE actions could reduce industrial material production (-59 Mt) and associated energy demand (-61 TWh). Overall, this could reduce the cumulated costs for industry decarbonisation by up to 72 bn€.

The results imply that a CE in residential and commercial EU buildings could reduce the future deployment of costly energy carriers and technologies required for achieving climate targets, namely hydrogen and CCU/S. While overall GHG emissions only decrease slightly, one could argue that the marginal emissions are the most complex to avoid. Our results emphasise the prospective role of a CE for the decarbonisation of the EU industry sector by reducing dependency on material imports and contributing to more stable supply chains.

On the one hand, this highlights the relevance of considering the contribution of a CE in EU industry decarbonisation scenarios to support policy making. Potentials for achievement of the EU climate targets was not fully considered due to the hitherto limited consideration of CE in energy system models. While some of these potentials are uncertain, such CE scenario should be compared with existing scenario to show diverse pathways for future developments. Future works should aim to integrate various modelling approaches to capture the multiple facets of a CE in line with sustainable development targets.

On the other hand, our results necessitate the development of policies to support the exploitation of these potentials. This is particularly relevant for mid- and downstream CE actions, which are uncertain and underrepresented in current EU policy. Such policies should split financial burdens between actors, incentivise stronger collaboration along the value chain and facilitate changes in user behaviour.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Meta Thurid Lotz: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Khaled Al-Dabbas:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Formal analysis. **Matthias Rehfeldt:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology. **Andrea Herbst:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Tobias Fleiter:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Ernst Worrell:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Meta Thurid Lotz reports financial support was provided by European Commission. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data are made available as supporting information.

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